

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetics

Genetics of seedling elongation in rice

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We studied the inheritance of seedling elongation ability in an F_2 population of Pankaj/Nageribao under deepwater conditions during the 1977 wet season at the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack. F_2 30-day-old seedlings and parental lines raised in shallow pans were submerged in 80 cm water. Seedling height was recorded after 10 d. The frequency distributions of F_2 s and parents are presented in the table.

Frequency distribution of parents and F_2 for seedling elongation in Pankaj/Nageribao. Cuttack, India, 1977.

Plant height (cm)	Frequency distribution		F_2
	Parents		
	Pankaj	Nageribao	
0-10	—	—	—
10-20	—	—	2
20-30	—	—	6
30-40	—	—	4
40-50	—	—	5
50-60	3	—	17
60-70	19	—	26
70-80	8	—	46
80-90	—	2	70
90-100	—	8	99
100-110	—	16	97
110-120	—	3	61
120-130	—	1	11
130-140	—	—	2
Range (cm)	54.0-78.2	89.4-120.7	
Average	67.2	110.4	

In 446 F_2 plants, 270 were 90-140 cm tall, with elongation rates equal to that of the Nageribao parent; 60 plants showed poor elongation (10-70 cm), comparable to Pankaj; and 116 were intermediate (70-90 cm), elongation ability better than that of Pankaj but not equal to that of Nageribao.

The data are consistent with two dominant complementary genes for elongation ability. Presence of both genes (*Sel 1* and *Sel 2*) gave elongation ability like that of the Nageribao parent. Absence of either of the genes resulted in segregants with intermediate elongation ability; absence of both resulted in plants like the Pankaj parent. □

Breeding methods

Use of Purple Puttu rice variety as a pollen barrier in CMS line seed production

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We assessed the distance of pollen dispersal across lines of Purple Puttu 90 d after sowing, which coincides with anthesis in the CMS lines now available at the Coimbatore Paddy Breeding Station. Purple Puttu has long duration (150 d) and is highly photoperiod sensitive (120 d to flowering in the wet season, does not flower in the dry).

Glass slides smeared with vaseline and acetocarmine-glycerine were tied at 60 cm high to bamboo stakes between six rows (15 × 10-cm spacing) of Purple Puttu. One gram fresh anthers collected at 0800 h from a number of varieties were bulked and kept in closed muslin cloth bags in a petri dish under

sunlight to 1000 h. The petri dishes were placed 15 cm from the first stake at the level of the glass slides and the muslin cloth removed to allow anther sacs and pollen grains to disperse by natural wind velocity (7.2 km/h to a height of 3 m). Three such dispersals were made.

The slides were collected and the number of anther sacs and pollen grains per square inch counted. Where there were no plants of Purple Puttu in front of the slide, anther sacs averaged 2.33 and pollen grains 12.66. After the first row of Purple Puttu, anther sacs averaged 1.66 and pollen grains 6.33 per square inch; after the second row, there

Rice pollen dispersal^a with Purple Puttu as a pollen barrier.

Purple Puttu row number	Av for 3 applications	
	Anthers/inch ²	Pollen/inch ²
0 row	2.33	12.66
Row 1	1.66	6.33
Row 2	—	0.33
Row 3	—	0.33
Row 4	—	—
Row 5	—	—

^a Wind velocity at 3 m = 7.2 km/h.

were no anther sacs, and pollen grains averaged 0.33 (see table).

At least 3 lines of Purple Puttu at 15 × 10-cm or closer spacing around CMS line seed production plots can effectively intercept pollen and anther sac dispersal between different cytotsterile lines. An added advantage is that Purple Puttu's purple foliage distinguishes it from other varieties. □

Inbreeding depression of yield in rice hybrids

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Seven IRRI medium-duration hybrids (130-140 d) were tested in 1986 wet season as F_1 (3 replications) and in 1987 dry season as F_2 (4 replications) for inbreeding depression of grain yield. Grain yields in the F_2 ranged from -28.59 to 3.62% compared to the F_1 (see table). The same F_1 and F_2 were